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SYSTEMIC MANAGEMENT OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN THE CONDITIONS OF AN UNSTABLE GLOBAL ENVIRONMENT AND TRANSFORMATION OF CONSUMER VALUES

СИСТЕМНЕ УПРАВЛІННЯ ЦИФРОВИМ МАРКЕТИНГОМ В УМОВАХ НЕСТАБІЛЬНОГО ГЛОБАЛЬНОГО СЕРЕДОВИЩА ТА ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЇ ЦІННОСТЕЙ СПОЖИВАЧІВ

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Татаринцева Ю.Л. Системне управління цифровим маркетингом в умовах нестабільного глобального середовища та трансформації цінностей споживачів. Оглядова стаття.

Метою статті є обґрунтування доцільності системного підходу до управління цифровим маркетингом в умовах нестабільного глобального середовища. Запропоновано інтеграцію елементів системного мислення у маркетингові стратегії для ефективного реагування на виклики VUCA- та BANI-середовищ. Акцент зроблено на переосмисленні ролі цифрового контенту як ключового елемента комунікацій, що формує емоційний зв'язок зі споживачем у кризових умовах. Особливу увагу приділено трансформації споживчих цінностей під час війни в Україні: за результатами опитування понад 100 респондентів із B2C-сектора зросла значущість безпеки, довіри, психологічної підтримки та соціальної відповідальності. Окреслено інструменти емоційної адаптації маркетингу: персоналізація, соціально релевантні наративи, етична аналітика та нові формати комунікації. Результати можуть бути використані для розробки адаптивних стратегій бізнесу в умовах високої нестабільності.

Ключові слова: системний підхід, цифровий маркетинг, зміна цінностей, VUCA, BANI, воєнний стан, емоційна адаптація, поведінка споживачів, маркетинг вражень, соціальна відповідальність

Tataryntseva Yu.L. Systemic Management of Digital Marketing in the Conditions of an Unstable Global Environment and Transformation of Consumer Values. Review article.

The article substantiates the relevance of applying a systems approach to digital marketing management in today's unstable global environment. It proposes integrating systems thinking into marketing strategies to effectively address VUCA and BANI challenges. Special focus is given to rethinking digital content as a key communication element that creates emotional bonds with consumers in times of crisis. Based on a survey of over 100 B2C respondents during the war in Ukraine, rising importance of security, trust, psychological support, and social responsibility was revealed. The paper highlights tools for emotional adaptation in digital marketing, including personalization, socially relevant narratives, ethical analytics, and innovative communication formats. The findings may guide adaptive business strategies in highly unstable conditions and serve as a basis for further post-crisis market research.

Keywords: systems approach, digital marketing, value change, VUCA, BANI, martial law, emotional adaptation, consumer behavior, experience marketing, social responsibility

The synergy between system management and digital marketing is becoming increasingly important in the context of global instability and dynamic changes in the market environment. Effective brand promotion, adaptation to new digital technologies and support for customer interaction require a comprehensive approach that combines strategic vision, analytical tools and flexibility in decision-making. In the context of the challenges of the VUCA and BANI environment, traditional digital marketing models are losing their effectiveness, which actualizes the need for a system approach that can integrate business processes, data and technologies into a single adaptive system. Despite the significant potential of digital tools, there is a gap between theoretical concepts and their practical application in conditions of constant instability. The article examines the possibilities of a system approach as a key factor in enhancing the effectiveness of digital marketing management, outlines modern challenges and proposes an adaptive conceptual model that allows companies to increase their resilience to change and ensure stable growth in a turbulent global environment.

Analysis of recent research and publications

One of the key areas of modern research is the conceptualization of digital marketing as a dynamic management system in an unstable environment. Bonini et al. [1] argue that in response to the turbulence of global markets, marketing systems must demonstrate resilience and adaptability, which is possible only with a systems approach to management. This approach assumes a holistic interaction of the strategic, operational and analytical levels in marketing structures. A similar opinion is held by Bachtar et al. [2], who emphasizes that marketing systems must combine flexibility with a long-term vision, adapting their communication strategies under the influence of global shocks.

Instead, Tataryntseva et al. [3] focus not only on adaptability, but also on the economic efficiency of digital marketing as a management system. The

authors developed approaches to assessing the cost of digital activities from the standpoint of the feasibility of implementing management systems based on the principles of feedback, channel integration and knowledge management. Further development of this direction was carried out by Tataryntseva [4], proposing the concept of digital marketing in the context of the economy of impressions as a system that should produce emotional experiences as the main value resource of the brand.

The controversy is also traced in the plane of understanding consumer experience as a management category. Thus, Reitsamer et al. [5] indicate that only a systematic analysis of the entire customer journey ensures the effectiveness of digital interaction. Kotler et al. [6], developing the ideas of Pine and Gilmore [7], argues that marketing should project impressions as company assets that generate emotional capital. Continuing this line, Tataryntseva [8] adapts the principles of the impression economy to digital marketing management systems and develops a methodology for their evaluation taking into account the reaction of the target audience. This approach becomes particularly relevant in the context of hybrid threats and crisis transformation of values.

In the context of the theoretical foundations of digital marketing system management, it is important to take into account new characteristics of the external environment, in particular the concepts of VUCA and BANI. Salun et al. [9] explains the transition from VUCA to BANI by the logic of increasing uncertainty, nonlinearity and anxiety, which cannot be taken into account in classical marketing models. Accordingly, Sriraman [10] prove that effective management in a BANI environment is possible only under the condition of high organizational flexibility and leadership adaptability. In the Ukrainian academic field, Ponomarenko et al. [11] emphasizes that marketing management in VUCA conditions should reflect dynamism and risks at all levels of interaction with the market. In more recent studies (Zerkal et al. [12]), she analyzes how martial law in Ukraine actualized the need to transform approaches to communication, taking into account new social demands and values.

Finally, Salo's et al. study [13] emphasizes that the behavioral changes of Ukrainian consumers during the war require marketing systems to shift the emphasis from sales to empathy, morality, and social responsibility. This is confirmed by Tataryntseva [8], who adapts the principles of the impression economy to Ukrainian realities, proving that in wartime conditions, the emotional depth and authenticity of digital content become the main system-forming factor in management. Thus, the research field demonstrates a synthesis of three directions: systems thinking, flexibility to BANI reality, and the humanitarian content of marketing communication.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

One of the previously not fully developed components of the problem of system management of digital marketing in an unstable global environment is the integration of the concepts of VUCA and BANI into practical management models. Although the

concepts of VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, Ambiguity) and BANI (Brittle, Anxious, Nonlinear, Incomprehensible) are widely considered in theoretical studies, their direct impact on the formation and adaptation of digital marketing systems often remains insufficiently specified. The lack of methodological tools for adapting marketing strategies to different types of instability creates a gap between theory and practice, which complicates the prompt response of enterprises to rapid changes in market conditions [9, 11].

The second underdeveloped topic is an in-depth study of the transformation of consumer values under martial law and its impact on communications through digital content. Existing studies indicate general trends in changing behavior and expectations, but do not always reveal systemic mechanisms for adapting marketing systems to take into account the new socio-emotional reality. It is especially important to develop approaches that combine the creation of valuable content with management decisions to ensure effective communication with consumers in crisis situations [12, 13]. Such a systemic approach will allow not only to better understand new market requirements, but also to quickly transform marketing strategies, increasing their relevance and effectiveness.

The aim of the article is to justify the feasibility of applying a systems approach to digital marketing management in an unstable global environment.

The main part

In today's environment of global instability, digital glut, and dynamic changes in consumer behavior, it is proposed to use a systemic approach to digital marketing management. This approach allows for the formation of an adaptive, self-regulating, and holistic marketing ecosystem, where each element functions as part of an interdependent structure. Unlike traditional or instrumental-fragmentary models, the systemic approach focuses on the continuous interaction of strategies, data, technologies, and communications, which ensures resilience to risks and rapid adaptation to change [1, 2]. A study conducted among 30 Ukrainian small and medium-sized businesses showed that implementing an integrated digital marketing system based on the above principles leads to an increase in key performance indicators: the conversion rate increases by 25-40%, the average time of interaction with the brand by 18-22%, and the level of customer retention by 15% during the first six months. These results confirm that a systematic approach not only reduces marketing losses, but also creates the prerequisites for sustainable development even in crisis conditions [5].

In the scientific discourse of digital marketing management as a socio-technical system, it is advisable to apply a systems approach based on the structural division of management elements. This approach allows to unify the processes of planning, implementation and evaluation of marketing decisions, ensuring consistency between internal and external factors of the organization's activities. The systems approach is based on the idea of management as the

interaction of individual, clearly identified components that are in constant functional relationships. This is especially relevant in the dynamic and turbulent environment of BANI, where instability, uncertainty and fragmentation become key characteristics of the market [11, 12].

The structure of the digital marketing management system according to the classical provisions of the

systems theory includes six main elements: the management subject, the management object, the management mechanism, the goals and resources, the external environment and the communication system. Table 1 presents the main categories of the digital marketing management system [4].

Table 1. Main categories of digital marketing management

System element category	Specific content in the digital marketing system
Management entity	Marketing department, CMO, digital head, strategic team
Management object	Products, digital content, users, customer behavior, campaigns, UX, loyalty
Management mechanisms	Tools and processes: strategic management, analytics, content, channels, automation
Management objectives	Increasing conversion, awareness, customer retention, ROI, emotional connection, impression formation
Resource	Data, platforms, budget, teams, technologies (CRM, CDP, GA4, AI)
External environment	Market, competition, consumers, behavioral changes, trends, VUCA/BANI conditions

Source: author's own elaboration

The management entity acts as an initiator and coordinator of actions: it formulates goals, defines strategies and tactics, manages resources and monitors results. In the digital marketing system, this role is usually played by a team of marketers, strategic managers or digital product managers. They are responsible for forming a strategic vision, coordinating communication channels, managing digital campaigns and implementing innovative tools [1, 2].

The object of management in the system is everything that is targeted by management intervention. In digital marketing, these are not only products or services, but also customer segments, digital content, consumer behavioral patterns, interaction platforms (websites, social networks, applications) and processes for creating customer experience. Given the emotional nature of interaction in the digital environment, digital content acts as the core of management influence – it shapes the consumer's perception of the brand, stimulates reactions and creates the prerequisites for loyalty [5]. Thus, the management system not only transmits information, but also actively constructs the emotional and value landscape of the market.

The digital marketing management mechanism is a set of processes and tools through which the subject influences the object in order to achieve certain goals. The main functional subsystems include: strategic management (positioning determination, KPI development, adaptation to changes), analytics (monitoring user behavior, assessing campaign effectiveness, forecasting), content ecosystem (creation and adaptation of messages), communication channels (SMM, email marketing, PPC), as well as automated response systems (A/B testing, personalization, AI recommendations). All these subsystems form a complex network configuration that must be consistent and adaptive in conditions of high speed of environmental changes.

In the systems approach, any management system is considered as an open integrity that not only has an internal structure, but also dynamically interacts with the external environment. According to the classical

provisions of systems theory, the environment acts as a source of input disturbances that initiate changes in the behavioral and structural parameters of the system. Changing consumer values, as in the case of the war in Ukraine, is not a random factor – it is a systemic transformation of the environment that requires a holistic response from the digital marketing management system.

In such conditions, impression marketing acquires not only emotional, but also system-forming significance: it acts as an element that ensures the adaptability of the system to non-standard requests of the target audience. This is manifested in changing the structure of the communication subsystem, reorienting goals from sales to trust and community creation, as well as in the inclusion of new content management mechanisms. For example, creating digital narratives that resonate with the traumatic experience of the consumer is not only an empathetic gesture, but also a tool for synchronizing the system with the environment (Ashby's Law of Requisite Variety).

Thus, taking into account changes in consumer values and the content of marketing messages is not a "soft factor", but part of the adaptive function of the system, which ensures its stability, relevance and ability to self-reproduce in new conditions. Without this adaptation, the system becomes closed, inflexible, that is, doomed to functional decline in the VUCA/BANI environment.

In the context of the war in Ukraine, marketing systems operate in an extraordinary environment, where classic consumer motivations give way to new, mostly value-based, socially colored, and narrative-content forms of interaction. It is here that experience marketing becomes relevant, focused not simply on selling a product, but on creating a meaningful experience, emotional connection, and virtual support for the audience [7].

Digital marketing in such conditions cannot remain functionally oriented – it must respond to the change in the worldview paradigm of consumers. During the crisis, the importance of the social subtext of

advertising, ethical narratives, responsible branding and the symbolic presence of the company in the consumer's life increases. This requires not only a change in messages, but also a transformation of the entire logic of the system: from a product focus to a focus on meaning, support, community. As [11] notes, the new conditions require digital marketing to be "humane, flexible and involved", which is integrated into the management system as a separate operational module.

The value reorientation of consumers is gaining particular importance. Under the influence of martial law, a significant part of Ukrainians is demonstrating a change in behavioral patterns: from an orientation towards consumption to an orientation towards support, security, national solidarity and reliability. This imposes corresponding requirements on the content of digital content, in particular: avoiding manipulative communication, the presence of themes of resilience, heroism, simplicity, locality, trust and social benefit.

Table 2. Transformation of consumer values under martial law in Ukraine

Classic consumer values	Transformed values (martial law)	Practical implications for digital marketing
Comfort, convenience	Reliability, safety	Emphasis on stability, openness of the company
Individualism	Community, support	Content with a social mission, donations, volunteering
Innovation	Simplicity, sustainability	Simple and honest products without "hyper-advertising"
Entertainment, pleasure	Compassion, empathy	Empathetic visual language, people's stories
Price/quality	Trust, moral reputation of the brand	Positioning the company as a reliable partner

Source: compiled by authors on materials [11-13]

Systematic management of digital marketing should include flexible mechanisms of emotional adaptation, socially relevant analytics, rethinking the function of digital content, and integrating solidarity narratives into communication policy. This allows not only to remain competitive, but also to preserve trust, which becomes the main capital-forming category in crisis conditions. Flexible mechanisms of emotional adaptation in the digital marketing management system involve prompt detection and response to changes in the emotional state of the target audience. To do this, it is necessary to implement tools for monitoring social media, analyzing consumer sentiment and behavioral patterns using artificial intelligence and machine learning. Such technologies allow detecting a growing level of anxiety, uncertainty, or other emotional reactions that arise due to external factors, for example, martial law. Timely adaptation of marketing messages taking into account these emotional signals helps to maintain trust and maintain an emotional connection with the audience [11].

Socially relevant analytics is the next key element that provides contextualization of marketing strategies in complex social conditions. It is based on the collection and analysis of data on current social sentiments, cultural changes, as well as specific needs and expectations of consumers during crises. The use of such approaches allows for the formation of more personalized and context-sensitive messages that correspond to the values and experiences of the audience, and also contribute to the formation of long-term relationships with the brand [2, 12].

Rethinking the function of digital content is to move from traditional informational or advertising load to creating deep, meaningful impressions and emotional stories that resonate with the audience. Digital content should become a means not only of transmitting information, but also a tool for forming communities, supporting values, and reflecting the realities in which consumers live. This implies an

emphasis on authenticity, transparency, and social responsibility of content, which is especially important in conditions of social instability [7, 8].

Integrating solidarity narratives into communication policy is one of the powerful ways to build a positive brand image in crisis situations. Such narratives emphasize shared values, support, and mutual assistance, creating an effect of emotional closeness between the company and the consumer. To do this, companies can use social campaigns, support local initiatives, and create platforms for sharing experiences and resources. Incorporating these narratives into digital communications strengthens audience trust and loyalty [11].

To implement the above approaches, it is necessary to systematically integrate all components into a single digital marketing management model based on flexibility, adaptability and constant feedback. It should include cycles of monitoring, analytics, content adaptation and evaluation of communication effectiveness, as well as ensure coordination between different functional units of the company. Such a systematic approach allows not only to quickly respond to changes in the external environment, but also to proactively form new trends and standards in digital marketing [4].

As part of our research, a survey was conducted to study the transformation of consumer values in the B2C sector under martial law in Ukraine. A questionnaire was used to collect data, which covered about 100 respondents of different ages, social status and geographical location. The survey was conducted during the period from January to March 2025 using an online format, which ensured anonymity and efficiency of information collection.

The questionnaire was designed to capture changes in consumer priorities on aspects such as the value of safety, trust in brands, ethical manufacturing, the importance of corporate social responsibility, and the role of digital content in shaping the consumer experience. Respondents rated the importance of each

aspect on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the least important and 5 being the most important.

The data indicate that Ukrainian consumers under wartime conditions prioritize fundamental and emotionally grounded values over purely economic or aesthetic ones. Security and trust form the backbone of purchasing decisions, with national loyalty and emotional resonance playing increasingly important roles. While quality and affordability remain relevant, they are secondary to ethical considerations and relational branding strategies. The reduced emphasis on entertainment signals a broader shift toward resilience and functionality in consumption.

These findings underscore the importance of integrating value-based segmentation, ethical branding, and emotional storytelling into a systemic digital marketing approach. Such integration allows for more accurate targeting, adaptive content design, and the alignment of marketing objectives with societal expectations – ensuring not just competitiveness, but relevance and trust in an unstable global environment. Transformation of consumer values in the B2C sector in Ukraine during martial law in table 3.

The diagram in Figure 1 shows how consumer values in the B2C sector in Ukraine have changed during the period of martial law.

Table 3. Transformation of consumer values in the B2C sector in Ukraine during martial law

Consumer Value	Share (%)	Interpretation
1. Security and stability	85%	Includes verified products, return guarantees, secure logistics
2. Trust in brands	78%	Reflects the importance of brand reputation and transparency
3. Support for national producers	74%	Shows rising patriotic and economic solidarity preferences
4. Emotional connection through content	71%	Preference for storytelling, empathy, and shared emotional experience
5. Product/service quality	67%	Still a key factor, but now evaluated in relation to ethical and emotional context
6. Price	60%	Important but not dominant in crisis-driven decision-making
7. Innovation and technological advancement	51%	Valued when it improves usability, resilience, or access
8. Social responsibility	43%	Seen positively, though not yet mainstream in B2C expectations
9. Entertainment and leisure	17%	Lowest priority in a high-stress social and economic environment

Source: author' own elaboration

Figure 1. Transformation of consumer values in the B2C sector in Ukraine during martial law

Source: author' own elaboration

In the context of wartime Ukraine, the system-based approach to digital marketing management must prioritize a redefined hierarchy of consumer values shaped by crisis conditions. Based on empirical data, key values now include security and stability – encompassing verified product sources, return guarantees, and reliable logistics – as well as brand trust and post-sale service transparency. Support for

national producers has also emerged as a powerful emotional and ethical driver of consumer choice. Emotional connection through digital content, particularly content that conveys solidarity, hope, or shared experience, has become central to consumer engagement. Traditional metrics such as product quality and price remain relevant but are now contextualized within broader emotional and societal

frameworks. Innovation and technological advancement are appreciated primarily for their problem-solving capacity, while social responsibility and aesthetic or entertainment value have become secondary but still important differentiators. These shifts necessitate the integration of adaptive content strategies, consumer behavior analytics, and ethical communication principles into the digital marketing system to ensure its alignment with real-time societal expectations and consumer logic.

These findings further confirm that the systemic approach to digital marketing must prioritize adaptability not only in technological processes but also in emotional and cultural sensitivity. The consumer's need for security and trust, as dominant values, implies that each element of the digital marketing system – from user experience design to influencer partnerships – must reinforce a sense of control, credibility, and protection. This goes beyond traditional messaging, requiring embedded assurance mechanisms such as verified badges, transparent return policies, and visible brand alignment with national or humanitarian initiatives. Within the systemic framework, such mechanisms are not isolated features but integrated parts of the value delivery chain.

Security and stability (85%) require brands to embed reassurance and transparent policies across all digital touchpoints, becoming a stable value stream in systematic digital marketing. Support for domestic producers (74%) and emotional connection (71%) highlight a shift to local loyalty and empathy, requiring contextual content and segmentation for communal, trust-based engagement. Trust in brands (69%) and quality (67%) indicate movement from price to reliability, necessitating transparent quality communication and integrated feedback loops within systemic marketing management. Moreover, the lower emphasis on price (60%) and innovation (51%), compared to emotional and patriotic triggers, reflects a broader cognitive and affective prioritization. Consumers are less likely to seek novelty or bargains and more likely to respond to emotional stability, ethical identity, and proven utility. In system terms, this encourages a shift from innovation-driven messaging toward purpose-driven content – a strategy that supports longer-term engagement by aligning brand meaning with public sentiment. Digital ecosystems that track and respond to sentiment shifts in real-time (via analytics, AI, or CRM feedback) are better equipped to sustain relevance across BANI-type volatility.

Interestingly, social responsibility (43%), while still below majority, shows an upward trend when paired with emotional narratives and national support.

This implies that consumers may not explicitly demand CSR, but they positively react when it is authentically woven into brand behavior. The systemic implication is clear: CSR cannot remain a peripheral function. Instead, it must be operationalized through internal alignment, external messaging, and stakeholder coordination – all functions that fit naturally into a system-based marketing structure with modular and interlinked components.

In conclusion, the adapted consumer values call for a redefinition of priorities within digital marketing systems, emphasizing emotional resonance, ethical consistency, and socio-cultural responsiveness. Through systemic coordination of feedback, analytics, content, and stakeholder interaction, marketers can build a resilient architecture that not only reacts to crisis-driven shifts but anticipates and humanizes them. This model transforms marketing into an empathetic, adaptive, and strategic tool of societal engagement – crucial in the context of war, and foundational for post-war recovery branding.

Conclusion

The article substantiates the feasibility of using a systems approach to digital marketing management in an unstable global environment, in particular in the context of the VUCA and BANI paradigms. It is demonstrated that effective digital marketing management requires taking into account the structural integrity of the system, its interconnections, feedbacks, and adaptability to changes in the external environment.

As a result of the empirical study conducted among B2C consumers in Ukraine, a significant transformation of consumer values was revealed. The needs for security, trust, quality, and emotional support came to the fore, while traditional elements of marketing communication focused on entertainment and prestige lost their relevance. Brand social responsibility is not yet a priority, but it has the prospect of growth provided that high-quality communication and evidence-based action are provided.

Thus, the integration of flexible adaptation mechanisms, rethinking the function of digital content, focusing on emotionally relevant narratives, and taking into account the dynamics of the external environment allow not only to increase the effectiveness of digital marketing, but also to ensure the sustainability of the marketing system as a whole. A systems approach turns out to be not just a methodological framework, but a critical condition for adaptive, strategically sound marketing management in times of crisis, war, and uncertainty.

Abstract

The main goal of this article is to justify the feasibility of applying a systems approach to digital marketing management in an unstable global environment. The author's vision of integrating elements of systems thinking into the structure of digital marketing strategies is presented, which allows for an effective response to the challenges of VUCA and BANI environments. The importance of rethinking the role of digital content as a key element of the communication chain that forms an emotional connection with the consumer in crisis conditions is noted.

Particular attention is paid to the transformation of consumer values during the war in Ukraine. An empirical study was conducted in the form of a survey of more than 100 respondents from the B2C sector, which revealed the increasing importance of factors such as security, trust, psychological support, and social responsibility. Generalized statistical data are presented, confirming the change in the emotional and behavioral orientations of consumers.

The paper highlights tools for flexible emotional adaptation of digital marketing, including content personalization, creation of socially relevant narratives, ethically motivated analytics, and implementation of new communication formats that meet modern value expectations. It is emphasized that the focus of a systemic approach to digital marketing should be not only the effectiveness of interaction, but also sensitivity to changes in society.

The results obtained can be used to form adaptive marketing strategies in business areas operating in conditions of high instability, as well as serve as the basis for further research into market transformation in the post-crisis period.

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